

DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION (DI) FOR GRADE 9 ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the effect of using differentiated instruction in teaching the different kinds of verbal to grade 9 students in TSNHS, Trinidad, Bohol for S.Y. 2017-2018. Specifically, it identified the research subjects' scores before and after using DI, and the significant difference between the pre-posttests scores. It employed quasi-experimental to estimate the causal impact of DI as an intervention on the learning of verbals on the target population. Match pair design with t-statistics was utilized to determine the significant differences between the pre-posttests scores of the respondents in the use of verbals. The findings revealed that with the use of DI, all posttests' scores showed an increase compared to the pretest scores, and that there is a consistent significant difference between all the pre-posttests scores of the students in gerund, infinitives and participle. Thus, it is concluded that Differentiated Instruction (DI) facilitated the effective teaching and learning of verbals: gerund, infinitives and participles. This study recommends for teachers to use DI in teaching verbals to students especially in heterogenous classes and to utilize the learning packet in teaching verbals.

Keywords: *Grade 9 English, Teaching Verbals, Differentiated Instruction, Learning Packet, Quasi Experimental, Match Pair Design, Trinidad, Bohol*

INTRODUCTION

The importance of grammar skills extends beyond academic boundaries into a variety of areas of life, including education, leadership, and professional success (Smith, 2015). Grammar skills not only enhance written communication but leadership effective and facilitates language acquisition, especially for non-native speakers (Brown, 2012 & Jones, 2013). Despite the importance, teachers often face challenges to effectively engage

students in grammar lessons, as evidenced by reports from English teachers in Tagum Sur National High School, Trinidad District, Bohol, Philippines which grammar proficiency levels, specifically in school year 2016-2017, especially in oral language, still being below average which affected the school's general performance test results.

Given the critical role that grammar plays in academic achievement, it is important to address this issue because of its subsequent implications for performance-based compensation for teachers. One of the major considerations is the strategies that educators use in teaching grammar to students. They should remember that different students perform differently for each student comes to school with unique academic needs and background experiences, culture, language, personality, interests, and attitudes toward learning (Tomlinson & Allan, 2012). Knowing this, teachers recognize that all of these factors affect how students learn in the classroom, and they adjust or differentiate their instruction to meet students' needs.

The Philippine Constitution of 1987, Article XV, Section 2, and Section 21 Chapter 2 of the Education Act of 1982 emphasizes the government's vision that each school should mold children the best way possible in order for them to become the prime movers of the society. This will be realized and achieved when a strong foundation is built in every student. However, analyzing the proficiency level of students in the Philippines, the real picture can be seen—learners struggle to learn basic skills, especially grammar. Middle school and high school teachers are often caught up in the dilemma of weighing content area expectations against the need to motivate students to become confident and curious learners. Differentiated instruction is a strategy that addresses student needs and preferences while also respecting the high demands of accountability in meeting the standards set by the department to ensure quality in education (Tomlinson, 2014). Differentiation embraces many of the processes, strategies, and approaches supported by best practices and researches (Smith & Tomlinson, 2012). While not confined to a single content area or a specific grade level, the differentiated approach to classroom instruction is one that can be applied to any content area at any grade level.

Thus, this study seeks to investigate the effectiveness of differentiated learning in improving grammar skills among high school students. Further, this study aims to bridge the gap in instructional approaches by investigating whether differentiated instruction based on Jerome Brunner's constructivist theory and Howard Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences can effectively meet students' diverse learning needs and improve their grammar skills.

Bruner's Constructivist Theory (1961) emphasizes the importance of instruction to align students' existing knowledge and conceptual frameworks, emphasizing active engagement and the gradual building of understanding. Similarly, Gardner's (1983) Theory of Multiple Intelligences emphasizes that the individual is unique among people, which means educational strategies need to be integrated with educational strategies and integrate these concepts. This study is creating attempts to complete discrimination procedures with students with diverse collections and educational priorities.

While differentiated instruction can be done in many ways-content, process, product and/or content until product differentiation (Tomlinson, 2014), in this study, the researcher differentiates the process in which the students learn the same lesson content in various ways but shall undergo the same assessment to check their understanding. With the adoption of this approach, teachers can provide customized learning experiences that meet students' individual needs and encourage learning outcomes. Through a comprehensive examination of the effectiveness of differentiated instruction in grammar instruction, this study seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse on innovative instructional practices and their impact on student learning outcomes.

Research Questions

This research assessed the effect of differentiated instruction in teaching verbals to Grade 9 students in Tagum Sur National High School, Trinidad, Bohol during school year 2017-2018 as basis for a proposed learning packet.

Specifically, this answered the following questions:

1. What are the students' scores before and after being exposed to differentiated instruction on the proper use of the following verbals:
 - 1.1 gerund,
 - 1.2 infinitive, and
 - 1.3 participle?
2. Are there significant mean differences between the students' pretests and posttests Scores on the aforementioned variables?
3. What learning packet can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at Tagum Sur National High School located at the center of Tagum Sur, Trinidad, Bohol which is situated three kilometers along the national highway from the center of its municipality with one-section grade 9 class with 45 students serving as the subject of the study. This class was taken as participants in the conduct of the pre-posttests on verbals as this research employed quasi-experimental which is an empirical intervention study used to estimate the causal impact of an intervention - Differentiated Instruction on target population without random assignment. It identifies a comparison group that is as similar as possible to the treatment group in terms of baseline through pretest-posttest (same class). The same students served as the subject of the grammar class where differentiated instruction was applied.

In order to gather the needed data to complete the study, the researcher utilized grammar tests referring to a set of tests administered to the respondents for the purpose of determining the students' performance in grammar, specifically verbals, before and after

the application of differentiated instruction in grammar class. This test was in two parts” pretest and posttest which have been both adapted from the internet and secondary English textbooks. Few modifications were considered to facilitate differentiated instruction, especially in the posttests. However, the researcher has added briefers to each test for clarity. The components in both pretest and posttest are the same. However, they vary in the way the test items are constructed and introduced. The students answered each of these tests as guided by the instructions provided for. Grammar pretest and posttest answers of research subjects for each and every item in all the tests in the three kinds of verbal: gerund, infinitive and participle, could either be correct or not correct. For every correct answer per number, a score of one was noted or given. For every wrong answer, 0 score was acquired.

The data gathered were statistically treated for the analyses and interpretations which collectively served as the findings. T-test was used to treat the significant differences between the respondents’ pre-posttests scores in the uses of the different kinds of verbal before and after being exposed to differentiated instruction. The scores were collected from the administered pretests and posttests. Statistical parameters and formula were used to measure and evaluate the scores of the respondents. These scores were compared to answer the problem of the study on the pre-posttests performances of the research participants. The T-tests for paired samples was utilized to determine the significant differences between the pretests and posttests scores of the respondents in the uses of gerund, infinitive and participles before and after applying differentiated instruction.

RESULTS

Table 1
Pre-Posttest Scores of the Respondents in the Use of Gerund

Scores	Pretest		Posttest		Result
	Frequency	Accumulated Score	Frequency	Accumulated Score	
10	0	0	5	50	Gained
9	0	0	11	99	Gained
8	0	0	14	112	Gained
7	0	0	12	84	Gained
6	0	0	3	18	Gained
5	2	10	0	0	Decreased
4	8	32	0	0	Decreased
3	18	54	0	0	Decreased
2	13	26	0	0	Decreased
1	3	3	0	0	Decreased
0	1	0	0	0	Decreased
Total	45	129	45	363	Gained
Mean	2.777778		8.066667		Gained
Median	3		8		Gained
Mode	3		8		Gained
Standard Deviation	1.0420145		1.115999		Gained

Table 2**Pre-Posttest Scores of the Respondents in the Use of Infinitive**

Scores	Pretest		Posttest		Result
	Frequency	Accumulated Score	Frequency	Accumulated Score	
10	0	0	7	70	Gained
9	0	0	13	117	Gained
8	0	0	7	56	Gained
7	0	0	13	91	Gained
6	0	0	5	30	Gained
5	1	5	0	0	Decreased
4	6	24	0	0	Decreased
3	19	57	0	0	Decreased
2	11	22	0	0	Decreased
1	5	5	0	0	Decreased
0	3	0	0	0	Decreased
Total	45	113	45	364	Gained
Mean	2.511111		8.088889		Gained
Median	3		8		Gained
Mode	3		8		Gained
Standard Deviation	1.140618		1.29373		Gained

Table 3**Pre-Posttest Scores of the Respondents in the Use of Participles**

Scores	Pretest		Posttest		Result
	Frequency	Accumulated Score	Frequency	Accumulated Score	
10	0	0	7	70	Gained
9	0	0	13	117	Gained
8	0	0	10	80	Gained
7	0	0	14	98	Gained
6	0	0	1	6	Gained
5	0	0	0	0	Decreased
4	15	60	0	0	Decreased
3	21	63	0	0	Decreased
2	6	12	0	0	Decreased
1	3	3	0	0	Decreased
0	0	0	0	0	Decreased
Total	45	138	45	371	Gained
Mean	3.066667		8.244444		Gained
Median	3		8		Gained
Mode	3		8		Gained
Standard Deviation	0.863397		1.131282		Gained

Table 4

Significant Difference between the Pre-Posttest Scores in the Use of Gerund

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	<i>Post</i>	<i>Pre</i>
Mean	8.066667	2.777778
Variance	1.245455	1.085859
Observations	45	45
Pearson Correlation	0.208461	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	44	
t Stat	26.1096	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.02E-28	
t Critical one-tail	1.68023	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.04E-28	
t Critical two-tail	2.015368	
Significantly different		
Reject Ho		

Table 5

Significant Difference between the Pre-Posttest Scores in the Use of Infinitives

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	<i>Post</i>	<i>Pre</i>
Mean	8.088889	2.511111
Variance	1.673737	1.30101
Observations	45	45
Pearson Correlation	0.107126	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	44	
t Stat	22.94786	
P(T<=t) one-tail	2.04E-26	
t Critical one-tail	1.68023	
P(T<=t) two-tail	4.08E-26	
t Critical two-tail	2.015368	
Significantly different		
Reject Ho		

Table 6

Significant Difference between the Pre-Posttest Scores in the Uses of Participles

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	<i>Post</i>	<i>Pre</i>
Mean	8.244444	3.066667
Variance	1.279798	0.745455
Observations	45	45
Pearson Correlation	0.122547	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	44	
t Stat	25.99119	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.23E-28	
t Critical one-tail	1.68023	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.46E-28	
t Critical two-tail	2.015368	
Significantly different		
Reject Ho		

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents in the uses of gerund achieved through ten-item test for both pretest and posttest.

Data in this table revealed that for scores 1 to 10 in the pretest, frequency of responses and accumulated scores were found in the lower bracket from 0 to 5. However, in the posttest, there is an observed opposite concentration of scores. Frequency and accumulated scores were noted and tallied in the upper scores from 6 to 10.

This rundown of pre-posttests scores signaled gains in the upper scores from 6 to 10, while it shows decrease in the lower scores from 5 down to 1. This resulted to a high increase in the pre-posttest mean from 2.78 to 8.07 leading to other significant increase in median and mode from 3 to 8. Moreover, it is revealed that pretest with a mean of 3 Sd=1.04 median and mode from 3 to 8. Moreover, it is revealed that pretest with a mean of 3 Sd=1.04 is lower than the posttest mean at 8 (Sd=1.12).

This could further tell that posttest scores which resulted from the use of DI for gerund increased compared to pretest scores. Definitely differentiated instruction brought an increase to the students' scores in the posttest on gerund. However, the variance results

(Sd) of 1.04 and 1.12 are not that big which signify those abilities are heterogenous, meaning the students were of differing level of intelligence.

The finding is supported by Stravroula et. al (2011) in a study on DI where it was proven that DI positively affects diverse students' characteristics.

With table 2, the pretest and posttest scores of the participants in the uses of infinitives before and after applying differentiated instruction are presenting the frequencies of the students getting the upper scores of 6 until the perfect score of 10 tallying an increase in the posttest versus the pretest scores. The posttest mean at 8.08 (Sd=1.29) is a little bit higher than the pretest mean at 2.5 (Sd=1.14).

The presented data showed a vivid positive effect of using differentiated instruction in teaching infinitives. Increase in pre-posttest scores is evident. The Sd values at 1.14 and 1.29 also show students' differing intelligences.

Subban (2006) and Stronge (2004) supported this finding in their claims that there could be increase in learners' performance if the teacher has addressed their learning differences. With DI, the teacher's approach may have affected very well the acquisition of the learning competencies (Wilson 2009).

Table 3 presents that the posttest scores tallied another increase in the frequency of the scores from 6 until 10 as the perfect score. The scores of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 manifested decrease in number. This is relatively higher than the pretest with the mean at 3.07 (Sd=0.86) compared to post at 8.24 mean score (Sd=1.13).

These data revealed another positive impact of DI, however this time, in the teaching of participle. Frequencies and accumulated scores both emphasized increase. Standard Deviation (Sd) values at .086 and 1.13 provide another evidence for students' multiple intelligences. DI must have surely brought about this improvement in scores as supported by Stravroula et .al (2011), Subban (2006) and Stronge (2004).

Data presented from table 1 to table 3 testify that with the application of Differentiated Instruction in learning verbals: gerund, infinitive and participle students could achieve better scores compared to pretests which did not employ DI. Though the increase in frequencies in the identified scores did not show consistency as manifested in the variations of frequencies of increase, student posttest scores in totality soared up. This is supported by the consistent increase of mean values from 3 to 8 in all pre-posttests results

in all three kinds of verbal. This could mean that DI facilitated the improvement of students' performance in the three components of verbal.

Table 4 indicates that the mean scores in the pre-posttests on the uses of gerund were significant at 0.05 level having the probability (P) value at 2.04-significant leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

This strengthened the claim that DI positively affected the posttest scores of the students in gerund making them higher compared to pretest scores. Hence, it is safe to say that DI is effective based on the data.

Table 5 bears the statistical computation on the difference in the pre-posttests test results of the participants in the uses of infinitives showing the computed probability value (P) at 4.08 signifying significant difference between the pre-posttests scores of the students in infinitives.

The same with gerund, the teaching of infinitive was also done applying DI. Hence, this significant difference in scores from low to increasing numbers could also be attributed to the use of differentiated instruction.

Compared with the result on gerund, the significant difference between the preposttest scores of the participants in infinitives as shown in the significant increase of scores

in the posttest compared with the pretest, made it also more evident that the exposure to DI does not only apply to increase in scores on gerund, but to infinitives as well. This then makes it safe to conclude that DI is effective for both gerund and infinitives.

Table 6 presents the statistical treatment result on the difference between the preposttests scores of the students in the uses of participles identifying significant difference between the students' scores in the pretest and posttest on the uses of participles as made evident in the statistical result of the probability value (P) at 2.46. This directed to the rejection of the null hypothesis for participle.

Tables 4, 5 and 6 on the significant differences between the pre-posttests scores of the students in gerund, infinitives and participles, consistently disclosed that there are significant differences in the pretests and posttests results among all the three kinds of verbal.

This finding, fully supported and strengthened the claim that DI facilitates the teaching of the different uses of gerund, infinitives and participles as verbals. DI is effective in teaching all kinds of verbal. There has been remarkable increase of scores in the posttests after students' exposure to DI versus the pretest scores. This identified increase is consistently proven with the results of all probability values of significant differences between pre-posttests scores in all three kinds of verbal.

Differentiated instruction resulted to the achievement of students' improved performance from the pretests to the posttests in the three kinds of verbals. Differentiated instruction

brings forth learning in the classroom when it facilitated effective teaching and effective student learning in the use of the different kinds of verbals: gerund, infinitives and participles.

Conclusions

With all posttests' scores in three kinds of verbal showing an increase compared to the pretest scores, and with the significant differences between the students' scores in the pretest and posttest in the uses of all the three kinds of verbal, the study drew out that Differentiated Instruction facilitated the effective teaching and learning of verbals: gerund, infinitives and participles of the Grade 9 students in Tagum Sur National High School, school year 2017 to 2018.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and the conclusion of the study, it is suggested to;

1. Use DI in teaching verbals to students especially in heterogenous classes.
2. Utilize the learning packet in teaching verbals.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, the researcher adhered to strict ethical standards, prioritizing the rights and dignity of all participants, while striving to obtain valuable and accurate data. The researcher diligently observed, adhered to and ensured that the following key ethical principles.

Informed Consent. Participants were carefully informed about the purpose of the study, procedures, possible risks or benefits, and how their information would be used. This was done through a fully informed consent form distributed prior to the study, giving participants ample opportunity to review, ask questions, and ultimately submit their consent for it. It was clear that participation was voluntary, and participants had the unequivocal right to withdraw from study at any point, with no consequences

Confidentiality and Anonymity. Participant privacy and confidentiality were strictly maintained throughout the study. Personal data and comments were handled more discreetly, and the anonymity of the participants was ensured, especially in the presentation and publication of the study results. To this end, participants were protected by pseudonyms or codes during data analysis and reporting, and data were securely hidden from unauthorized access.

Prevention of Plagiarism. The researcher strictly followed the principles of academic integrity by carefully describing and crediting all materials used in the research and Originality and authenticity is paramount, and information was obtained directly from

participants and analyzed in the specific context of the study. In-text citations and a comprehensive bibliography were used to ensure clarity of sources to acknowledge all contributions.

Establishment of Contact. The researcher maintained a strong commitment to fairness and objectivity, which ensured that no conflict of interest would compromise the conduct or interpretation of the research. Transparency and honesty were maintained throughout, and any potential conflicts were immediately identified and addressed to support the integrity and honesty of the survey results.

Bias Mitigation. Findings were interpreted with great diligence to prevent the introduction of bias. The research procedures were conducted objectively, with an unwavering commitment to accurate and transparent presentation of results. Rigorous review and peer review processes were used to minimize the impact of personal bias, and to ensure the validity and reliability of the survey data.

By unwaveringly applying these ethical standards, the researcher not only upheld the rights and well-being of the participants but also ensured the reliability of the research results kept authentic that she only used the findings gained through this process to further knowledge and understanding in the field.

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